

CHEMISTRY

UTILIZATION OF PLANT WASTE FOR FERTILIZER PRODUCTION

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Abstract

In this study, pistachio waste, vegetable residues, and grass biomass were processed using a rapid composting method. The main goal was to evaluate the alterations in physical and chemical parameters during the composting process. It also focused on determining the quality level of the final compost products. The process was carried out under aerobic conditions. The results showed that all piles of compost passed the normal mesophilic and thermophilic stages. All samples reached a stable maturation phase. Variations in humidity, pH, and nutrient content depended on the raw ingredients used. The final compost showed characteristics of maturing compost, such as dark color and homogeneous structure.

Key words: composting; plant waste; organic waste management; agricultural residues; soil fertility.

Introduction

Plant waste is one of the main kinds of organic waste generated on a massive scale in modern times as a result of agricultural, food industry, and urban activities. As pointed out in the scientific literature, these wastes are considered not only an environmental problem but also a biological resource with significant potential. Studies show that the volume of plant residues generated during global agricultural production can be measured in billions of tons. However, a significant portion of these residues continue to be used inefficiently. The generation of plant waste takes place across various sectors, and its quantity varies depending on the intensity of economic activities [5].

The largest percentage belongs to the agricultural sector. During crop production, lots of residues are generated after harvesting. These include wheat and barley

straw, corn stalks, rice husks, sunflower stems, cotton residues, and other lignocellulosic materials. The agricultural industry and agro-processing enterprises are also important sources of plant waste. During the processing of fruits and vegetables, peels, seeds, pulp, and other organic residues are generated. These wastes are characterized by high moisture content and rapid biodegradability. According to FAO data, approximately one-third of the food produced globally is recorded as loss and waste, a large percentage of which consists of plant-derived residues. In Azerbaijan, plant waste is often classified as “non-hazardous industrial waste” or as the biological fraction of municipal solid waste. According to recent statistics, the amount of waste generated over the years is as follows:

Figure 1. Annual generation of plant waste by type. The blue line represents fruit and vegetable waste, the orange line indicates grass waste, and the green line shows pistachio waste.

The utilization of plant waste depends directly on its physical, chemical, and biological properties. In Azerbaijan's agricultural sector, the significant amount of plant waste generated requires this resource to be considered not merely as waste, but as a "strategic raw material."

Traditional disposal techniques such as landfilling and incineration are not considered efficient. Moreover, they do not provide any significant economic benefits. According to research, plant waste mainly consists of hemicellulose, cellulose, and lignin. While cellulose and hemicellulose are relatively easy to decompose, lignin has a more complex structure and slows down the biodegradation process [10]. This property is one of the key factors in selecting appropriate biological treatment methods. Composting is one of the fastest and safest ways to return this material to the nutrient cycle [4].

Composting is a process in which organic waste is converted into a useful product under aerobic conditions through the activity of microorganisms. Compost improves moisture retention, enhances infiltration, and increases soil hydraulic conductivity. There is general agreement in the literature that compost stimulates plant growth, improves flowering and fruiting, and enhances the presence of beneficial microorganisms in the soil. Composting occurs in two main stages: the mesophilic stage (25–45 °C) and the thermophilic stage (45–85 °C). These stages are driven by the activity of

microorganisms such as bacteria, fungi, and actinomycetes, which act according to environmental physical and biochemical conditions [1,12]. During the composting process, complex organic molecules undergo various transformations because of microbial degradation. The duration of conventional composting typically ranges from 90 to 120 days, depending on the raw materials, method, and degree of stabilization and maturity.

The "Berkeley method" allows compost to be made in approximately three weeks. This method requires several initial conditions: the particle size of raw materials should be between 1.3 and 4 cm (approximately 0.5–1.5 inches), the carbon-to-nitrogen (C:N) ratio should be around 30:1, the moisture content should be maintained at about 50%, and the compost pile dimensions should be approximately 1.0 × 1.0 × 1.0 meters.

Experimental

In this study, pistachio shells, different types of fruit and vegetable peels (such as apples, bananas, potatoes, etc.), and grass waste were used. These materials are considered suitable for raw materials for composting due to their high organic matter content.

The composting procedure was carried out under laboratory conditions using small-scale containers. The materials used were pre-shredded before the process.

Figure 2. Homogenization of plant waste materials using a laboratory homogenizer during the experimental process

Pistachio shells were mixed with straw to improve structure and ensure proper aeration. A homogenizer was used to reduce the particle size of the materials.

Each type of waste was composted separately in individual containers. During the composting process, the moisture content was maintained at approximately 50–60%. For this purpose, small amounts of water were added to the mixtures every 2–3 days.

To maintain aerobic conditions and ensure sufficient oxygen supply, the compost mixtures were turned twice a week, approximately every 3–4 days. This also

contributed to a more uniform decomposition process [2,9].

The total composting period lasted 4 weeks (28 days). The first 7 days represented the initial active decomposition stage, followed by an intensive biological decomposition phase from day 7 to day 21. The final stage, from day 21 to day 28, was the stabilization phase.

At the end of the process, all three samples resulted in dark-colored, homogeneous, soil-like compost.

Figure 3. Shredded waste materials used in the study (dry grass, dry pistachio shells, wet pistachio shells, fresh grass, and fruit and vegetable waste) in transparent bags.

Figure 4. Compost preparation process showing sequential layering of soil, waste, and soil in the experimental setup.

During the study, the obtained compost samples were first dried at 65 °C. The samples were then grounded in a laboratory mill to a particle size of 1 mm for analysis and stored in transparent plastic bags. The prepared samples were analyzed using an organic element analyzer and an ICP spectrometer.

For the determination of pH and electrical conductivity (EC), 1 g of each compost sample was mixed with 5 mL of distilled water (1:5 ratio). The mixture was shaken on a shaker for 30 minutes, after which pH and EC values were measured.

pH measurements were carried out using a Mettler Toledo pH meter, while electrical conductivity was determined using a Mettler Toledo conductivity meter. The moisture content of the samples was determined by drying them at 105 °C for approximately 24 hours.

The total carbon (C), hydrogen (H), and nitrogen (N) contents in both raw materials and compost samples were determined using an elemental analyzer.

Aluminum foil containers were used for sampling, and 2.5–3.5 g of each sample was taken. The analytical process was carried out based on a modified Dumas method using the principle of dynamic combustion. This process lasted approximately 13 minutes, and the determination of carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen, and sulfur was performed at 950 °C. The oxygen content was determined using the pyrolysis method [7].

During ICP-OES analysis, argon and nitrogen gases were used. Argon gas was employed to generate a high-temperature plasma environment. When the samples were introduced into this plasma, the elements within them became excited and emitted light at characteristic wavelengths.

The emitted optical spectrum was measured using an ICP-OES optical emission spectrometer, allowing the determination of macro- and microelements as well as heavy metal concentrations in the samples.

Results and discussion

During the grass composting process, mass loss was calculated during the conversion of waste into compost. Initially, a compost pile consisting of 120 g of raw material (fresh green grass and straw) was prepared. After a 20-day rapid composting process, the

mass decreased to 70.8 g. This indicates a significant reduction in mass and demonstrates the efficiency of the process.

At the end of the composting process, characteristics typical of mature compost were observed in all samples, including stabilized temperature, fine texture, dark brown or black color, and a homogeneous structure.

Table 1.
Elemental composition (macro- and microelements and heavy metals) of pistachio, vegetable and fruit, and grass compost samples (mg kg⁻¹)

	Total Al (mg kg ⁻¹)	Total B (mg kg ⁻¹)	Total Ca (mg kg ⁻¹)	Total Cd (mg kg ⁻¹)	Total Co (mg kg ⁻¹)	Total Cr (mg kg ⁻¹)	Total Cu (mg kg ⁻¹)	Total Fe (mg kg ⁻¹)	Total K (mg kg ⁻¹)	Total Mg (mg kg ⁻¹)	Total Mn (mg kg ⁻¹)
Pista- chio com- post	82.1	1.8	1004	0.0	0.2	0.4	0.5	840.6	777.4	126.6	2.7
Vege- table and fruit com- post	27.26.1	1.3	1961	0.0	0.3	0.9	0.8	246.3	837.2	220.6	6.4
Grass com- post	7361.1	0.3	906.2	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.3	50.7	370.5	93.2	2.4

The concentrations of macroelements, microelements, and heavy metals in pistachio compost, vegetable and fruit compost, and grass compost are presented in Table 1. The results indicate noticeable differences in elemental composition depending on the type of raw material used.

Vegetable and fruit compost showed the highest calcium (Ca) content (1961 mg kg⁻¹), as well as relatively high magnesium (Mg) and manganese (Mn) levels. Pistachio compost exhibited higher iron (Fe) and potassium (K) concentrations compared to the other samples. In contrast, grass compost was characterized by a significantly higher aluminum (Al) content

(7361.1 mg kg⁻¹), while most other elements were present in lower amounts.

Cadmium (Cd) was not detected in any of the samples, indicating the absence of this toxic heavy metal. Other heavy metals such as cobalt (Co), chromium (Cr), and copper (Cu) were found only in very low concentrations.

Overall, the results demonstrate that the elemental composition of compost strongly depends on the source material, which in turn influences its potential application in agriculture.

Figure 5. Carbon, hydrogen, and nitrogen contents in pistachio, vegetable and fruit, and grass compost samples.

The diagram presents a comparison of total carbon (C), hydrogen (H), and nitrogen (N) contents in pistachio compost, fruit and vegetable compost, and grass compost. The results show that carbon content was highest in pistachio compost (39.05%) and lower in fruit and vegetable compost (31.41%) and grass compost (31.12%). Hydrogen content followed a similar trend, with pistachio compost having the highest value (4.57%), while fruit and vegetable compost (3.78%) and grass compost (3.85%) showed slightly lower values.

In contrast, nitrogen content was highest in grass compost (3.08%), followed by pistachio compost (2.48%) and fruit and vegetable compost (2.14%). These differences indicate that the elemental composition of compost varies depending on the raw materials used, with pistachio compost being richer in carbon and hydrogen, while grass compost contains a higher proportion of nitrogen.

Moisture content in the different compost types ranged from 9% to 47%. The lowest moisture value (9%) was observed in compost prepared from vegetable and fruit waste. The highest moisture content (47%) was recorded in the compost produced from a mixture of pistachio solid waste and wet pistachio shells (50:50 ratio).

The pH values of pistachio and vegetable composts were within the range of 6–8.5, which corresponds to the acceptable standard range. The pH of these samples was close to neutral, varying between 7.8 and 7.9. However, the grass compost showed a slightly higher pH value (pH = 8.6), which slightly exceeded the recommended level.

Neutral or slightly alkaline pH values indicate that the compost has reached a stable condition.

Temperature variation during composting ranged from 22–62 °C in pistachio compost, 30–65 °C in vegetable compost, and 35–72 °C in grass compost.

In conclusion, the study demonstrates that different plant-based wastes can be successfully converted

into stable and high-quality compost through the composting process. The physical and chemical parameters confirm that the obtained products are suitable for agricultural applications.

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